

Physico-Chemical Studies of Emulsions : Part IV. Effect of Temperature on the Properties of Emulsions

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Effect of temperature on the properties and stability of oil-in-water emulsions with water and kerosene oil as continuous and disperse phases and sodium dioctyl sulphosuccinate, sodium dibutylsulphosuccinate (anionic surfactants); cetyl pyridinium bromide, cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (cationic surfactants) and polyoxyethylene sorbitan monostearate, alkyl aryl polyether alcohol (nonionic surfactants) as emulsifying agents have been studied. The value of surface tension, viscosity and specific gravity of emulsions decreases and conductivity increases with an increase in the temperature of emulsions.

Although surface-active materials¹, naturally-occurring substances² and finely-divided solids³ have been employed as emulsifying agents to prepare various types of medical⁴, biological⁵, technological⁶, cosmetic⁷, paint⁸, industrial⁹, agricultural¹⁰, asphalt¹¹, and food¹² emulsions, no systematic effort however has been made so far to find out the effect of temperature on the properties and hence stability of emulsions. In continuation of earlier work¹³⁻¹⁵, the present investigation deals with the effect of temperature on the properties and stability of emulsions, prepared by taking single surfactants (anionic, cationic and nonionic) as emulsifying agents and water and kerosene oil (K.O.) as external and internal phases.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium dioctyl sulphosuccinate (Manoxol OT) and sodium dibutyl sulphosuccinate (Manoxol 1B)-anionic surfactants; cetyl pyridinium bromide (CPB) and cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTMAB)-cationic surfactants and alkyl aryl polyether alcohol (Triton X 100)-nonionic surfactant. were B.D.H. England products and poly-oxyethylene sorbitan

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1. J. E. Carless and G. W. Hallworth, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1968, **26**(1), 75.
2. L. I. Conrad, *J. Soc. Cosmetic Chemists*, 1954, **5**, 11.
3. J. H. Schulman and J. Leja, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, **50**, 598.
4. B. S. Berlin, *Ann. Allergy*, 1962, **20**, 472.
5. E. A. Brown, *Geriatrics*, 1963, **18**, 27.
6. J. L. Moilliet, "Waterproofing and Water-repellency", p. 52, New York, Elsevier Publishing Co., 1963.
7. P. Mannheim, *Soap, Perfumery, Cosmetics*, 1962, **35**, 898, 1002, 1102.
8. J. C. Cowan and L. E. Gast, *Amer. Paint J.*, 1963, **47**, 85.
9. H. W. Parkins, *Petroleum Engr.*, 1951, **23B**, No. 4, 60.
10. J. K. Eaton, *Chem. Ind.*, 1962, **19**, 1914.
11. K. Letters, *Kolloid-Z.*, 1962, **1.82** 147.
12. L. H. Meyer, "Food Chemistry", p. 357, New York, Reinhold Publishing Co., 1960.
13. K. D. Jain and M. K. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 989.
14. K. D. Jain and M. K. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (Communicated).
15. K. D. Jain and M. K. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (Communicated).

monostearate (Tween 60) was obtained from M/s Koch-Light Laboratories Ltd., London. In all the experiments double distilled K.O. (b.p. 205° and sp.gr. 7948925 at 30°) and double distilled water (pH 6.2 and conductivity $\cdot 85 \times 10^{-6}$ ohm⁻¹cm⁻¹) were employed.

Preparation of emulsions : Agent-in-Water method¹⁶ was employed to prepare the emulsions under following conditions :—

- a) Definite ratio of K.O. and water (1 : 2)
- b) Definite concentration of emulsifying agent ($\cdot 05$ g.).

Properties of emulsions : Emulsion Type (O/W or W/O) was determined by the Dye solubility method¹⁷. Particle size was found out by taking a photomicrograph of the microscopic slide of the emulsion with the help of Carl Zeiss Jena Microscope fitted with attachment camera using 15×ocular and 40×objective¹⁸.

Viscosity, surface tension, specific gravity, conductivity and pH were determined by the usual Ostwald viscometer, stalagmometer, pycnometer, conductance meter with “magic eye” and Beckman pH meter respectively at 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45 and 50°.

The results are summarised in Table I–VI.

TABLE I

Emulsions stabilized by anionic surfactant

Emulsion Type: O/W; Manoxol IB = $\cdot 05$ g.; K.O. = 10 ml.; O/W ratio = 1 : 2;
Particle Size = 7–8 μ .

Temp. (°C)	pH	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Specific Gravity	Viscosity ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Surface Tension (dynes/cm)
15	7.20	4.6	.9146994	21.49456	53.90138
20	7.00	7.0	.9143798	18.72106	53.20180
25	6.85	9.5	.9140511	16.51868	52.39449
30	6.70	12.1	.9137105	14.69141	51.50576
35	6.60	14.8	.9133549	13.15060	50.53930
40	6.55	17.6	.9129813	11.85239	49.50299
45	6.50	20.5	.9125866	10.75999	48.42076
50	6.45	23.5	.9121674	9.83740	47.29457

16. P. Becher, “Emulsions : Theory and Practice”, p. 267, New York, Reinhold Publishing Co., 1966.
17. E. A. Hauser and J. E. Lynn, “Experiments in Colloid Chemistry”, p. 129, New York, McGraw-Hill Book Co., 1940.
18. C. P. Shillaber, “Photomicrography in Theory and Practice”, p. 41, New York, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1949.

TABLE II

Emulsions stabilized by anionic surfactant

Emulsion Type: O/W; Manoxol OT = .05 g.; K.O. = 10 ml.; O/W ratio = 1 : 2;
Particle size = 8-9 μ

Temp. (°C)	pH	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	Specific Gravity	Viscosity ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Surface Tension (dynes/cm)
15	7.40	6.0	.9141511	23.09402	52.80079
20	7.20	8.5	.9138632	20.16880	52.13190
25	7.05	11.1	.9135662	17.83926	51.35896
30	6.90	13.8	.9132573	15.90686	50.50619
35	6.80	16.6	.9129335	14.27965	49.58344
40	6.70	19.5	.9125917	12.89254	48.58666
45	6.65	22.5	.9122287	11.72696	47.54982
50	6.60	25.6	.9118414	10.74194	46.46375

TABLE III

Emulsions stabilized by cationic surfactant

Emulsion Type : O/W; CPB = .05 g.; K.O. = 10 ml.; O/W ratio = 1 : 2;
Particle Size = 7-8 μ

Temp. (°C)	pH	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	Specific Gravity	Viscosity ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Surface Tension (dynes/cm)
15	6.05	6.6	.9336622	17.14147	56.16010
20	6.20	9.0	.9333311	14.89098	55.41330
25	6.35	11.6	.9329928	13.12610	54.54768
30	6.45	14.4	.9326450	11.66302	53.60191
35	6.50	17.3	.9322852	10.42919	52.57532
40	6.50	20.3	.9319111	9.39457	51.48139
45	6.55	23.4	.9315202	8.52295	50.33437
50	6.55	26.5	.9311098	7.80211	49.14182

DISCUSSION

It has been observed that there is hardly any change in the stability of emulsions when the temperature of the emulsions is raised from 15° to 50°, but there is a difference in the value of properties of the emulsions at different temperatures.

TABLE IV

Emulsions stabilized by cationic surfactant

Emulsion Type : O/W; CTMAB = .05 g.; K.O. = 10 ml.; O/W ratio = 1 : 2;
Particle Size = 8-9 μ

Temp. (°C)	pH	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	Specific Gravity	Viscosity ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Surface Tension (dynes/cm)
15	5.80	7.5	.9331140	17.68051	55.55518
20	5.95	10.0	.9328146	15.37911	54.82530
25	6.10	12.6	.9325080	13.57291	53.98432
30	6.20	15.3	.9321918	12.07308	53.05318
35	6.25	18.1	.9318638	10.81081	52.05316
40	6.30	21.1	.9315215	9.74625	50.98112
45	6.35	24.2	.9311623	8.84949	49.85611
50	6.35	27.4	.9307837	8.10762	48.68607

TABLE V

Emulsions stabilized by nonionic surfactant

Emulsion Type : O/W; Tween 60 = .05 g.; K.O. = 10 ml.; O/W ratio = 1 : 2;
Particle Size = 6-7 μ

Temp. (°C)	pH	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	Specific Gravity	Viscosity ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Surface Tension (dynes/cm)
15	6.80	1.40	.9306953	16.26625	33.67148
20	6.80	1.45	.9304255	14.10248	33.44429
25	6.80	1.50	.9301483	12.40981	33.16071
30	6.80	1.60	.9298614	11.00507	32.83733
35	6.75	1.70	.9295623	9.82126	32.47607
40	6.75	1.85	.9292486	8.87060	32.07516
45	6.75	2.00	.9289176	8.07091	31.64647
50	6.70	2.20	.9285667	7.39516	31.18479

It may be seen from Tables I-VI that irrespective of the nature of emulsifying agent, surface tension of the emulsions decreases with a rise in the temperature of the emulsions. There is a fall in the value of viscosity as the temperature of the emulsions is raised. Conductivity of the emulsions increases with an increase in the temperature and specific gravity increases with a decrease in the temperature of emulsions.

TABLE VI

Emulsions stabilized by nonionic surfactant

Emulsion Type : O/W; TritonX100 = .05 g.; K.O. = 10 ml.; O/W ratio = 1 : 2;
Particle Size = 7-8 μ

Temp. (°C)	pH	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	Specific Gravity	Viscosity ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Surface Tension (dynes/cm).
15	6.65	1.50	.9301793	16.80396	33.23943
20	6.65	1.55	.9299412	14.58946	33.01925
25	6.65	1.60	.9296958	12.85416	32.74381
30	6.65	1.70	.9294407	11.41544	32.43223
35	6.60	1.85	.9291734	10.20201	32.08056
40	6.60	2.00	.9288914	9.22146	31.68973
45	6.60	2.15	.9285923	8.39672	31.27178
50	6.55	2.35	.9282733	7.70081	30.82451

In case of anionic surfactants (Table I and II), pH decreases with an increase in the temperature of the emulsions and the tendency of the emulsions to become acidic from alkaline increases. From Tables III and IV, it is clear that with cationic surfactants, the pH value of the emulsions increases with increase in temperature and the emulsions remain acidic. For emulsions stabilized by nonionic surfactants (Tables V and VI) there is very slight decrease in the value of pH with increase in temperature.

It may be concluded that although there is no visual change in the stability of the emulsions between 15 and 50°, however the value of surface tension, viscosity and specific gravity of emulsions decreases and conductivity increases with an increase in the temperature of emulsions irrespective of the fact whether the emulsions are stabilized by anionic, cationic or nonionic surfactants.

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